

An Empirical Investigation into the Utilization of Information Resources by Academic Staff in Some Selected Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract:- Academic Libraries are very vital to the tertiary education system because of their support to education in general. It plays an important role in the teaching and learning process. This research work will therefore investigate the utilization of information resources by academic staff in some selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi state. The specific objectives of the study are to find out the level of availability of information resources in the institutions, and determine the extent of use of the materials by the academic staff. It is also to find out the factors that hinder the use of available information resources and make recommendations for improvement of library use. Five research questions will be formulated to guide the study. The study will employ the use of survey research design. The population of this study was 278 out of which 225 were sampled using Krejcie-and Morgan table of determining sample size. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire and the Statistical tool used was frequency counts simple percentage. Data collected for the study was analyzed using SPSS version 2.0. The 225 questionnaire administered were all retrieved from the respondents. This was achieved due to the sufficient time given for the respondents to fill the instrument and with the aid of research assistants used some of which are domicile in the institutions under study. The major findings of the study are that there are adequate library resources in the library of tertiary institutions in Kebbi State and that lecturers use the library mainly for consultation of books and reference materials. They also use it for research purpose and borrowing of books. Furthermore, lecturers utilized books more than other sources of information. A number of recommendations were put forward for improvement of library use but the most prominent suggestion was that more up to date and relevant information sources should be acquired for the library. Additional professional and para-professional library staff should be employed by the respective academic libraries. The staff found in the libraries as at the time of research was few and overstretched and more funds should be approved for the libraries to enable them meet up with all its financial obligations.

Keywords:- Investigation, Utilization, Information Resources, Availability, Academic Staff, Tertiary Institutions, Patrons.

I. INTRODUCTION

The primary aim of establishing an academic library is to support the objectives of its parent institution, which include among others, to promote teaching, learning and research. The academic library is meant to serve the academic and non-academic staff, students and members of the institutions. It is evident that the quality of any tertiary institution is measured by the quality of its library collections because of its exceptional role in the higher institution system. It is a well known fact that there can never be the existence of a tertiary institution without a library since institutions of higher learning are meant to teach and carry out research. For the teaching staff and research fellows, the academic libraries are supposed to provide information resources and services of sufficient quality and diversity [3].

Education and library are the two faces of same coin. One cannot exist without other. Hence, an academic library is an integral part of any institution of formal education. It supports the teaching- learning process of the institution it is attached with. Academic library can be defined as “a library which associated or attached with any educational institution to support its educational programmes” [9].

Depending upon the nature of the institution and its academic programmes, the library collection is developed. The students, academic and non-academic staff, research scholars, administrative and other staff of the institution are the users of the academic library [5]. These libraries are situated in universities, polytechnics and colleges of education among other tertiary institutions. The purpose of establishing these libraries is to meet the information needs of staff and students in the institutions they belong. The library is the heart of these institutions since all they do revolve round books. Basically, these libraries support all academic programmes offered in the institutions. The objective of academic include to serve the needs of the academic community; collect and store all kinds of reading and reference material; provide all kinds informational materials to support their curricular requirements; provide supporting materials for extracurricular activities; provide reading areas for users; render lending service appropriate to students, teachers and researchers and provide an active reference and information service [1][4].

The academic libraries have the statutory mandate of providing array of library services in the institutions that establish them. This entails making information materials available to different categories of library user to meet their information, education, entertainment and research needs. Academic libraries are also supposed to cater for all the areas of knowledge taught in the parent institution to advance knowledge and facilitate research. As a result, academic libraries are sometimes decentralized with a main library co-ordinating departmental and faculty libraries [2]. This is the state of affairs in academic libraries in Kebbi State where departmental libraries are often co-ordinated by the Central libraries for effective service delivery. For academic libraries to perform their various functions, its collection must not only include books but other materials such as general and specialized reference collections, made up of journals, newspapers, manuscripts, historical maps, government publications, clippings, letters, thesis and audio-visual materials.

Utilization of library resources entails using of library resources. A person or thing that uses something somewhere or someplace to achieve his or her purposes is an utiliser or user. In the same context, one can state that those who make use of the library materials for their benefits are library users or utilisers. Also, those who enter the library and find such library materials useful are library users. [19] also defined a user as “a person who uses one or more of library services at least once a year. Hence, people who go either to the public, private, special school or academic libraries for some genuine reasons, requiring the attention of the library staff, are known as the library users or utilisers. Library users in the universities can be divided up administratively into external and internal users. The internal users consist of undergraduates, post-graduates, academic staff, research fellows and other members of the tertiary institutions, while the external users are those who are not members of the institution, but are also served by the libraries but under certain specific official arrangement [6].

Academic libraries are mostly made up of subject readers who concentrate their use of library materials on areas of specialty. Students belong to these subgroups of subject's readers. Subject specialists or academic staff is also part of these subgroups, with the students obviously forming a high proportion of the users of academic libraries. The functions of any academic library are summarized in the promotion of teaching, learning and research[11]. These roles are prosecuted through balanced acquisition, proper processing, storage, interpretation and dissemination of relevant information. Anything on the contrary renders the institution impotent in achieving its mission [12]. Academic Libraries are therefore important because they are storehouse of information or records of human experience to which students, academic staff and researcher can utilize thereby quench their information thirst. The Libraries makes available and accessible to its patrons the information resources needed for teaching and learning. By offering instruction in the use of Library and bibliographical resources, the Library participates in the transition of knowledge.[16][18]

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

Academic library remains the nerves center if the institutions of higher learning, this is view of the outstanding roles in play in the advancement of teaching, learning and research. It is generally expected that resources provided by the academic libraries should be fully utilized in order to enhance teaching and learning. When an academic library is regularly used by academic staff, they often became up-date their knowledge in fields of specialization and become more effective in the discharge of their academic duties. With improved library patronage, the value of graduates produced by tertiary institutions will be high while academic staff can compete well with their counter parts in other tertiary institutions across the country.

The resultant effect of low or non patronage of information resources provided for consultation in academic libraries by academic staff will lead them not be up to date in their knowledge thereby reduces their efficiency during academic activities in their respective institutions and may likely not give out their best to students. They may also not be able to compete favourably with their counterparts in other institutions when it comes to presentation of papers and seminars. Also, the inadequate utilization of academic library's collection, will not justify the large sum of money spent on acquisition of materials and staff salaries. Similarly, it will likely affect the quality of teaching and learning in the institution. As a result of foregoing, it is likely that half baked graduates will be produced. [7] emphasized that it is important to know the extent of library utilization because one's impression of library use may be entirely different with what is on the ground. It is also true that such factors like number of hours a library is open and the library's programme of instruction amongst many other factors may influence library use and it is only by an investigation that the true cause may be established.

The investigation of tertiary institutions in Kebbi state, will enable us know the extent of Library use. It will also enable us know the availability of resources and purpose of patronizing academic libraries in tertiary institutions within the area under study [8]. It will also enable the researchers to bring to limelight extent of use of the academic libraries, unravel the key factors that hinders the use library resources and strategies that could be adopted to improve the use libraries by academic staff in Kebbi State tertiary institutions. It was observed academic libraries in Kebbi state tertiary institutions are most likely not adequately used especially by academic staff. This is the problem which the researchers feels that only an investigation will un-ravel the mystery and once problems are discovered and a solution found, academic staff will begin heavy patronage of the library.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

The general objective of this study is to investigation into the utilization of information resources by academic staff in some selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi state, Nigeria specifically, the study is:

- To find out the level of availability of library materials in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State.

- To uncover the purpose of use of information resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State.
- To determine the extent of use of library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State.
- To examine factors that hinders the use of the library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State.
- To establish the strategies that could be adopted to improve the use of library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State.

➤ *Research Questions*

This study is guided by the following questions.

- What is the level of availability of library materials in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State?
- What is the purpose of the use of library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State?
- What is the extent of use of library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State?
- What factors hinders the use of libraries resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State?
- What strategies could be adopted to improve the use of library resources by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State?

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The findings of the study will hopefully benefit the Management of Tertiary Institutions, the Academic Libraries, and the Lecturers of the tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. Also to benefit from these studies are the students and the general academic community in the selected institutions in Kebbi State. The management of the tertiary institutions will know the problems of the library, that is whether the library resources are available in good quantity or not, whether the information sources are current and up to date or not. They will know the problems that hinder proper patronage of the library by lecturers and students. They will also know whether the funds they have been approving for the library are adequate or not. The lecturers themselves will benefit from this study for the fact that the resources they indicated not available may be acquired. The recommendations of lecturers on how they can effectively use the library may be implemented for their good. Also the various information delivery methods through which information can be delivered will be exposed, thereby enabling librarians to know the specific ones they can demand for. The study will also add to the existing literature in the field of librarianship especially in the area of utilization of Library resources in tertiary in institution.

➤ *Research Design*

The research method or design to be adopted for this study will be the descriptive survey method. Descriptive survey method involves a study of a population through the use of sample. The findings obtained from studying the sample can be applied to the entire population. in [13][15]. The choice of this design was considered most appropriate because a large population is involved in the study. Descriptive survey method is aimed at collecting data and describing it in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population.

II. AREA OF THE STUDY

The study will be carried out in some selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. Kebbi is a state in north-western Nigeria with its capital at Birnin Kebbi. The state was created out from part of Sokoto State in 1991. Kebbi State is bordered by Sokoto State, Niger State, Zamfara State, Dosso Region in the Republic of Niger and the nation of Benin. It has a total area of 36,800 km² (14,200 sq mi). Kebbi State consists of 21 Local Government Areas (LGAs), four emirate councils (Gwandu, Argungu, Yauri and Zuru), and 35 districts. And it has a total population of 4,440,050 as at 2016 population census. The choice of Kebbi State for this study is because it houses a quite number of functional academic libraries.

➤ *Population of the Study*

The population of this study will comprise of all academic staff in the selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi State including Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State Polytechnic, Dakingari, Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi and School of Health Technology, Jega respectively. Out of which, the following institutions were selected considering the difference in institutional settings and type of academic programme therein.

S/N	Name of Institution	No. of Academic Staff	Sample Size
1	Federal University Birnin Kebbi	74	59
2	Kebbi State Polytechnic, Dakingari	54	44
3	Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu.	82	66
4	School of Nursing and Midwifery, Birnin Kebbi	68	56
	Total	278	225

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

➤ *Sample and Sampling Technique*

The population for this study was determined using Krejcie and Morgan table for determining sample size. Krejcie and Morgan table has been widely used by researchers to determine research population size. The total number of academic staff in the selected tertiary institutions was found to be 278 out which 225 was sampled and used for the study using Krejcie and Morgan [10].

➤ *Instruments for Data Collection*

The instrument employed in gathering data for this study was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed by the researchers. It was made up of four sections. Section A was on level of availability of library materials in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi, Section B was on why academic staff uses the library, Section C was on factors hindering the

use of the library by academic staff and Section D was on steps that could be used to improve the use of the library respectively.

➤ Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face validation. They were given to two experts, one in the Department of Library and Information Science, Kebbi State Polytechnic and another to the Department of Library and Information Science, Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi. Their comments, corrections and suggestions were all integrated into the final copy of the instrument.

➤ Method of Data Collection

The researchers administered copies of questionnaire meant for academic staff with the aid of trained research assistants. The distribution was done in each department and in offices of the academic staff of the selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. The distribution was done in two weeks while collection of the completed questionnaire took one week. After which an interview was organized with the respective heads of libraries of the selected institution on areas in the questionnaire that the researchers wanted more details

to be provided or areas that needed clarification. The data analysis was therefore based on the number of correctly filled and returned questionnaire by the academic staff.

III. METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data gathered through questionnaire was presented in tables while mean scores was used for the data analysis. A 4 point scale was used with a midpoint score of 2.5 criterion mean indicating acceptance while any score below the stated bench mark is considered negative response. For the percentage, 50% is regarded as positive and accepted while any below 50% is regarded as negative and not accepted.

The formular for this is $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$

\bar{X} = mean

\sum = summation

X = raw score

N = number of observations

IV. RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the level of availability of library materials in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State.

Lib. Resources	AA	A	FA	NA	\bar{X}	DECISION
Journals	46	67	112	0	2.70	Accepted
Research monographs	55	70	100	0	2.80	Accepted
Research reports	30	70	125	0	2.57	Accepted
Technical bulletin/report	61	86	78	0	2.92	Accepted
Data sheets	0	0	0	225	00.0	Rejected
Dairies	33	85	107	0	2.67	Accepted
Internal research reports	31	76	115	0	2.58	Accepted
Indexes/abstracts	33	72	120	0	2.61	Accepted
Biographies	35	58	132	0	2.56	Accepted
Gazetteers	53	84	88	0	2.84	Accepted
Guide & travel books	27	55	143	0	2.48	Accepted
Text books	29	68	128	0	2.56	Accepted
News paper	45	70	110	0	2.71	Accepted
Magazines	36	69	120	0	2.62	Accepted
Periodical	22	81	122	0	2.55	Accepted
Internet services	36	74	115	0	2.64	Accepted
CD Roms	33	82	110	0	2.65	Accepted
Cassettes (Audio)	33	87	105	0	2.68	Accepted
Encyclopedia	27	74	124	0	2.56	Accepted
Dictionaries	225	0	0	0	4.00	Accepted
Atlases, maps & globes	26	49	150	0	2.44	Rejected
Translated documents to indigenous language	35	14	74	102	1.46	Rejected

Key: - AA = Adequately available A = available FA = fairly Available NA = Not available.

Table 2 shows the mean responses on the level of availability of library materials. The mean scores shows that out of the 22 library materials listed, 19 have a score within the range of the stated bench mark of 2.50 scores and above indicating positive/acceptance response whereas 3 items scored below the acceptable range of 2.5 which implies negative response hence rejected. Materials with the lowest scores from the table include data sheets with a means score (0.00), Atlases, maps & globes (2.44) as well as Translated documents to indigenous language with (1.46) respectively.

Research Question 2: What is the purpose of use of library resources by lecturers in Tertiary Institutions, Kebbi State?

Table 3: Mean Responses on Why lecturers Use Library Resources in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State.

S/NO	Why do you go to the library	VA	A	FA	NA	\bar{X}	DECISION
1	To consult reference Materials and books	161	64	0	0	3.72	Accepted
2	To prepare lecture notes	142	58	25	0	3.52	Accepted
3	To read newspapers	91	63	71	0	3.09	Accepted
4	To borrow books	84	110	31	0	3.24	Accepted
5	For research purposes	133	72	20	0	3.50	Accepted

Key = VA = very appropriate A = appropriate FA = fairly appropriate NA = Not appropriate

Table 3 shows the mean responses on why lecturers use library resources in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State. From the table, it is glaring that all the mean scores on the items provided have been rated between 3.09 to 3.72. This means that the items have been rated positively and accepted since none of them falls below 2.5 mean score. This implies that all the lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State consult the library resources to use reference materials, to prepare lecture notes, to read newspapers, to borrow books and for research purposes. This consistent with the study conducted by [17], which found that one of primary reasons academic staff patronage the library is fulfill research needs by way of consulting relevant reference materials in the library.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of use of library materials by lecturers in Tertiary Institutions, Kebbi State?

Table 4: Mean Responses on the extent of use of Library Resources by Lecturers in Tertiary institutions in Kebbi State

S/N	Library Resources	VHE	HE	ME	LE	\bar{X}	DECISION
1	Books	191	34	0	0	3.85	Accepted
2	Journals	97	85	43	0	3.24	Accepted
3	Newspapers	99	74	52	0	3.21	Accepted
4	Research monographs indexes/abstracts	90	87	48	0	3.19	Accepted
5	Research reports	114	76	35	0	3.35	Accepted
6	Translated document to in digamous languages	0	30	50	145	2.48	Accepted

Key = VHE = very high extent, HE = high extent ME = moderate extent, LE low extent.

Table 4 shows the mean scores on the extent of uses of library materials. Results on the table indicated that all the library materials have a mean score of 3.19 and above with the exception of translated documents to indigenous languages which have a mean score of 2.48 which is below the bench indicating rejection. This means the library materials are rated positively and accepted, implying that all the listed library material such as books, journals newspapers, research monographs, indexes, abstracts, research reports and newspapers are used to a very high extent with books while translated document to indigenous languages being utilized to a low extent.

Research Question 4: What factors hinder the use of library materials by lecturers in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State.

Tables 5: Mean Responses on factors that hinder the use of Library Material by Lecturers in Tertiary Institution’s Library in Kebbi State

Factors that impede/ Hinder	AH	H	PH	DH	\bar{X}	DECISION
Non-involvement of teachers in book selection	150	42	25	8	3.59	Accepted
No up to date maternal	152	73	0	0	3.67	Accepted
Not many journals	131	69	25	0	3.47	Accepted
Users not informed of new arrivals	155	45	25	0	3.57	Accepted
Poor library instruction	89	76	58	0	3.11	Accepted
Unavailability of automatic generator	158	52	15	0	3.63	Accepted
Unavailability of air conditioners	160	40	25	0	3.60	Accepted
Inadequate library staff	160	40	25	0	3.60	Accepted

Key = AH = actually hinders, H = hinders, PH = partially hinder DH = don’t hinder.

Table 5 shows the mean response of factors that impede or hinder the use of library materials by lecturers. The mean scores shows that all the factors listed scored nothing less 2.5 and in fact scored 3.11 to 3.67 mean scores. By this, it means all the factors are rated positively and are accepted. They include non involvement of lectures in book selection, no up to date materials, not many journals, users not informed of new arrivals, poor library instruction, unavailability of automate generator, unavailability of air conditioners and inadequate library staff are factors that actually hinder the use of library materials by lecturers.

Research Question 5: What steps could be taken to improve use of library of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State by lecturers?

Steps to be taken to improve the use of Library Materials	VA	A	FA	NA	\bar{X}	DECISION
Buy more relevant books	158	40	27	0	3.58	Accepted
Buy more current information sources	153	72	0	0	3.68	Accepted
Buy multiple copies of books	131	58	36	0	3.42	Accepted
Fund library adequately	155	45	25	0	3.57	Accepted
More departmental libraries needed	90	77	58	0	3.14	Accepted
Increase professional staff	149	61	15	0	3.59	Accepted
Subscribe to more magazines	160	40	25	0	3.60	Accepted
Automatic generator needed	139	54	32	0	3.47	Accepted
Involve lecturers in book selection	143	49	33	0	3.48	Accepted
Improve library instruction	140	47	38	0	3.45	Accepted

Key = VA = very appropriate A = appropriate FA = fairly appropriate NA = Not appropriate

Table 6 shows the mean scores of steps to be taken to improve the use of library materials in Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State by lecturers. The mean scores revealed that all the above listed items are rated positively and accepted as none falls below 2.5 mean score. This means that all the items in the table are considered tenable steps to be taken in order to improve the use of the library materials in the Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State. Provision of more relevant books has a mean score of (3.58), more current information sources (3.68), multiple copies of books (3.42), Fund library adequately (3.57) and establishment of departmental libraries (3.14). Others include recruitment of more professional library staff with a mean of (3.59), purchase more magazines (3.60), provision of Automatic generator (3.47), Involve lecturers in book selection (3.48) and Improve library instruction (3.45) respectively.

V. DISCUSSION OF THE MAJOR FINDING

The findings and discussions in this study show that the library of the Tertiary institutions in Kebbi State has adequate library resources. Out of the twenty-two information sources listed, nineteen of them were found to be available. Only three of them namely Data sheets, Atlases, maps & globes and Translated documents to indigenous language were discovered not to be available. The only problem about the availability is that they are not adequately available but only fairly available. The implication is that not many lecturers will have access to them at all times. It is therefore the view of the researcher that more of those items should be procured to make them adequately available.

The findings and discussions on why lecturers use the library of the Tertiary institutions in Kebbi State show that the major reason is to consult books and reference materials. They also go to the library to read newspapers, borrow books and for research purpose. Not many of them go there for internet

browsing, probably because they have their laptops at home. The implication of this is that since there isn't multiple numbers of information sources, the lecturers consider the library as not being too relevant and don't visit there often.

The findings on extent of usage of library materials by lecturers in Tertiary institutions in Kebbi State reveal that the lecturers used more of books than other materials. The usage of books is closely followed by journals, newspapers, and research reports. The implication of these findings is that lecturers used more books because of their high availability compared to other information sources. Journals usage is meant to keep them abreast of new developments in their fields while they use research reports to know areas that have been investigated and those that need investigation. A further implication of a use of few information sources to the detriment of others is that the other information sources are not many in number and that their importance is not known.

The finding on impediment / hindrance to the use of the library of the Tertiary institutions in Kebbi State reveals that lecturers complain of inadequacy of current information sources. The implication is that once lecturers are not involved in book selection policy and more funds not made available to the library, the library will not acquire a lot of current information sources and that will not ginger more lecturers to frequently utilize the library resources.

On suggestions for improvement of the utilization library, the respondents agree with all the factors highlighted by researcher as they will help improve library patronage if put adequately in place. This means.

➤ *Summary of the Major Findings*

Based on the data presented and analysis, the findings could be summarized as follows:

- There are adequate library resources in the library of the Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State.
- Lecturer's main reasons for using the library of Tertiary Institutions in Kebbi State were to consult reference materials and books, borrow books, read newspapers conduct research and prepare lecture notes.
- The usage distribution of information sources by lecturers revealed that they used to a very high extent books, journals, newspapers researcher monographs, indexes/abstracts, research reports but most especially books.
- Lecturers were of the view that the major impediment to their use of the library was the inadequacy of current information sources, their non-involvement in book selection, and inadequacy of professional staff amongst other reasons.
- Several suggestions were put forward by lecturers for improving the library but the most prominent suggestions were acquisition or more current and up to date materials, proper funding of the library and acquisition of automatic generator.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from this research work, the following recommendations were put forward: -

- Current and relevant information sources particularly books and journals should be acquired. Multiple copies of heavily used books should be acquired by the library management.
- Additional professional and para-professional library staff should be employed by the respective academic libraries. The staff found in the libraries as at the time of research was few and overstretched.
- More funds should be approved for the Academic Libraries under study. This will enable the libraries to meet all its financial obligations.
- Lecturers should be regularly informed of newly acquired information sources. This could be done by sending list of currently received publications to each head of department. Lecturers should equally be involved in the book selection policy of the university.
- An automatic generator should be acquired for the library to be providing power in case of failure from the public supply. Similarly the air-conditioning system should be provided and made functional for the library.
- Library user education programme should be improved as many lecturers didn't participate in it. Many of those who participated were not satisfied.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study investigated into the utilization of information resources by academic staff in some selected tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to find out the level of availability of library materials in the Libraries, and determine the extent of use of the materials by lecturers. It is also to find out the factors that

impede library, use by lecturers and make recommendations for improvement of library use. The research design used is the descriptive survey method, which involves a study of a population through the use of sample. The total population of this study was 278 out of which 225 were sampled using Krejcie and Morgan table of determining sample size. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire and the Statistical tool used was frequency counts simple percentage. Data collected for the study was analyzed using SPSS version 2.0. The major findings of the study are that there are adequate library resources in the library of tertiary institutions in Kebbi State and that lecturers use the library mainly for consultation of books and reference materials. They also use it for research purpose and borrowing of books. Furthermore, lecturers utilized books more than other sources of information. A number of recommendations were put forward for improvement of library use but the most prominent suggestion was that more up to date and relevant information sources should be acquired for the library.

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